

Policy brief – Deliverable 6.4

How Artificial Intelligence redefines labour market vulnerability in Europe

From historical risks to future
resilience

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PATHS2INCLUDE

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European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations

Title: How AI redefines labour market vulnerability in Europe: from historical risks to future resilience

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Introduction

Over recent decades, labour market vulnerabilities have persisted across the European Union, disproportionately affecting certain social groups. However, the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) is poised to reshape this landscape, creating a need to anticipate how technological disruptions will alter the nature of employment vulnerability. It remains unclear whether these technologies will merely reinforce existing disadvantages or create new populations of at-risk workers.

Evidence from the PATHS2INCLUDE research highlights a specific "AI adaptability risk", which affects approximately 14% of the EU workforce (see Table 1 below). This concerns workers who face high exposure to AI-automatable tasks yet currently have limited digital skills' use. The groups most at risk of low AI adaptability only partly overlap with those who are currently most vulnerable. For women and late-career workers, existing vulnerabilities align with a higher likelihood of falling into the high-risk category of AI adaptability. By contrast, tertiary-educated employees – not typically considered vulnerable today – are also overrepresented among those facing a high risk of AI adaptability.

Drawing on insights from the PATHS2INCLUDE analysis "New and Changing Risks of Labour Market Attachment" (Magda & Krzakała, 2025), this policy brief aims to identify the socio-demographic profiles most exposed to future technological disruption. It compares historically vulnerable groups like migrants and less than tertiary educated with groups at risk due to AI adoption, providing recommendations for policymakers to support adaptability and prevent new forms of labour market exclusion.

2. Key research findings

The policy brief first outlines the definition of labour market vulnerability used and shows which socio-demographic groups are most vulnerable according to this category. It then introduces a categorisation of AI adaptability risk and describes the occupational and socio-demographic profile of workers at highest risk – those with high exposure to AI and currently limited use of digital tools at work.

2.1. Redefining labour market vulnerability in the age of AI

Crucially, new AI-related vulnerabilities on the labour market only partially overlap with historical labour market risks, such as gender. Women are disproportionately represented, accounting for 59% of high-risk employees compared to 47% of the total workforce, and late-career workers (55-64) also face elevated exposure (22% vs 20%) (see Table 1). Conversely, groups not traditionally perceived as vulnerable are now overrepresented in this high-risk category, specifically tertiary-educated employees (47% of the risk group versus 41% of the workforce). Migrants, who are traditionally perceived as vulnerable, are underrepresented in the AI risk group (see Table 1).

Table 1. Women, late-career workers and tertiary-educated individuals are overrepresented in the high AI adaptability risk group. The table presents the shares of socio-economic groups among (a) the whole 25-64 population, employed workers and vulnerable workers (b) AI risk among employed workers in the EU in 2022

Group	(a)			(b)
	All	Employed workers	Labour market vulnerable (underemployed/inactive/unemployed)	AI risk
Tertiary Education	37%	41%	26%	47%
Women	50%	47%	58%	59%
Age 25-34	23%	24%	23%	22%
Age 35-54	52%	56%	42%	56%
Age 55-64	25%	20%	36%	22%
Migrants	16%	15%	20%	14%
Parents	20%	22%	17%	22%
Whole population	100%	79%	28%	14%

Note: Countries have equal weights. Source: Own elaboration based on EU Labour Force Survey 2022. Interpretation: (a) In the EU population aged 25–64 in 2022, 50% were women. Among all employed workers, 47% were women, while among all labour-market-vulnerable individuals, 58% were women. (b) Among all employed workers at high risk of AI exposure, 59% were women.

2.2. Labour market vulnerability

Labour market vulnerability reflects varying degrees of weak attachment to the labour market, defined here through three distinct dimensions: economic inactivity, unemployment, and underemployment. Together, these categories capture the population of individuals who are either not working or are working below their full capacity. The group most distant from the

labour market consists of the economically inactive—individuals aged 15-89 who are neither working nor unemployed, often due to care duties, health issues, discouragement, or personal choice. By contrast, unemployed individuals are those actively seeking employment and immediately available to work. This definition relies on standardised survey data rather than administrative records, prioritising actual job search behaviour over formal registration to capture labour market engagement regardless of benefit status. Finally, vulnerability extends to the employed through underemployment. These individuals face limited job security and income potential because, despite wishing to work more hours, they are unable to do so because their employer does not offer additional hours or full-time positions.

In terms of demographic distribution, migrants, women, and those without tertiary education remain the most vulnerable groups (Valls et al., 2024). Migrants are overrepresented across aggregated vulnerability criteria, a disparity reinforced by intersectional patterns within the primary working-age group of 35-54 (see Table 2). The intersection of these risk factors creates acute disadvantages: among women, migrant parents with lower education levels face the highest vulnerability rate at 51%. For men, migrants similarly remain the most affected, with vulnerability rates ranging from 18% to 29%. While possessing tertiary education is generally associated with a lower risk, it does not fully insulate workers from structural disadvantages; migrants with tertiary education still face higher vulnerability than their native peers. Furthermore, family responsibilities continue to shape these outcomes, as parents – especially mothers – show weaker labour market attachment compared to non-parents (Buttler et al., 2025).

Table 2. Share of socioeconomic group with vulnerable status in the labour market (either underemployment, inactivity or unemployment) in the 35-54 age group, in 2022 in the EU

Group	Education	Parental status	Natives (%)	Migrants (%)
Women	Less than tertiary	Parents	33%	51%
		Non-parents	31%	42%
	Tertiary	Parents	15%	33%
		Non-parents	15%	30%
Men	Less than tertiary	Parents	15%	26%
		Non-parents	21%	29%
	Tertiary	Parents	11%	18%
		Non-parents	13%	22%

Interpretation: Among native mothers without tertiary education, 33% are either economically inactive, unemployed, or underemployed.

Note: Countries have equal weights. Source: Own elaboration based on EU Labour Force Survey 2022

2.2. AI adaptability risk

AI adoption introduces a new dimension of vulnerability linked to technological change. To assess whether AI-related labour market risks overlap with current ones, such as gender and education level, we assign each worker to an AI adaptability group. This classification is achieved by examining the combination of two dimensions: workers' use of digital tools, which serves as a proxy for their existing digital skills (Lipowska & Palczyńska, 2025), and their occupational

exposure to AI, which acts as a proxy for the extent to which AI can perform parts of their job (see Table 3).

Workers characterised by high AI exposure, but low digital tool use are considered the most vulnerable to AI adoption. These individuals may struggle to adjust because AI is increasingly capable of handling their cognitive and interpersonal tasks, while their limited digital skills make it challenging for them to utilise these new tools effectively. Consequently, they face potential vulnerability in the future labour market, risking falling behind as digitally skilled colleagues or new entrants leverage AI to become more productive. This "adaptability risk" group accounts for 14% of the EU workforce and includes occupations such as teaching professionals and sales workers.

The socio-demographic groups most commonly found in this high-adaptability-risk category do not fully overlap with those currently identified as vulnerable. For women and late-career workers, existing labour market vulnerabilities coincide with high AI adaptability risk. In contrast, people with tertiary education – who are not typically considered vulnerable today – are overrepresented in the AI-adaptability-risk group. Furthermore, while migrants are overrepresented among the currently vulnerable, they are notably underrepresented in the high-AI-risk group.

Table 3. AI adaptability groups

AI adaptability group	High adaptability risk	Technologically ready		No adaptability need
		Exposed to AI	Not exposed to AI	
AI Exposure	High	High	Low	Low
Digital device use	Low	High	High	Low
Typical occupations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching professionals • Sales workers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal, social and cultural associate professionals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information and communications technology professionals • General and keyboard clerks • Business and administration professionals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science and engineering professionals • Science and engineering associate professionals • Health professionals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cleaners and helpers, • Agricultural, forestry and fishery labourers • Building and related trades workers
Share of EU workforce	14%	34%	12%	40%

Source: Own elaboration based on EU Labour Force Survey 2022 data.

3. Policy implications

Based on these PATHS2INCLUDE research findings, a central priority must be the development of digital skills (such as data management, communication, and using job-specific software) for workers facing a high AI adaptability risk. This group, which combines substantial exposure to AI with limited use of digital tools, accounts for approximately 14% of the EU workforce and is heavily concentrated in occupations such as teaching professionals, sales workers, and legal, social and cultural associate professionals. To bridge this divide, policies should prioritise accessible, occupation-specific training that directly addresses the digital-tool gaps identified in the analysis.

Furthermore, supporting women and late-career workers is vital for the resilience of EU growth, particularly given their overrepresentation in the high AI-adaptability-risk group. This necessitates targeted measures to promote gender equality in the labour market, alongside specific support for an aging workforce. As the number of labour-market entrants declines, future economic growth will increasingly depend on boosting labour productivity rather than expanding labour supply. However, older workers face distinct challenges, being disproportionately exposed to AI-affected tasks while engaging in comparatively limited use of digital tools. Tailored programmes are therefore crucial to help these workers adapt to changing task requirements, enabling them to remain active for longer and strengthening overall labour-market resilience in the face of demographic pressures.

Finally, labour-market policies must adapt to include groups newly exposed to technological change, as AI-related risks cut across traditional lines of vulnerability. The research results indicate that tertiary-educated workers - a demographic not typically considered vulnerable - are now overrepresented in the high-risk category. Consequently, state intervention in the labour market should broaden its scope to ensure that support systems extend to these newly affected groups, preventing them from falling behind in the digital transition.

Further reading

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